

The impact of placement and work motivation on employee performance in the Gorontalo Provincial social service office

Nursapitri Djarati *, Sukarman Kamuli and Ismail Djakaria

Master of Public Administration, Postgraduate Program, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

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Abstract

The problem in this research is the lack of leadership motivation and placement that is not in accordance with the employee's educational background on employee performance, making employees less than optimal in completing their tasks and work. This research is descriptive quantitative research with a correlation design that aims to determine the influence of placement and work motivation on employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office. The results of this research show that: 1) The test results show that the t_{count} value for the placement variable is greater than the t_{table} ($2.858 > 0.677$). So, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive influence from the placement variable on the employee performance variable partially (individually). 2) The test results show that the t_{count} value of the motivation variable is greater than t_{table} ($6.848 > 0.677$). So, H_0 is rejected and H_2 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive influence of the motivation variable on the employee performance variable partially (individually). 3) The test results show that the t_{count} value for the placement and motivation variables is greater than the t_{table} ($1.264 > 0.677$). So, H_0 is rejected and H_3 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive influence of each placement and motivation variable on the employee performance variable partially (individually). From the data analysis, it can be concluded that placement and motivation together have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. From this conclusion, the impact resulting from this research is that good motivation by the leadership and placement in accordance with the educational background will improve employee performance.

Keywords: Placement; Work Motivation; Employee Performance; Social service office

1. Introduction

Flippo (2000: 58) defines HRM as the planning, organizing, directing, and controlling of the procurement of labor, development, compensation, integration, maintenance, and termination of human resources to achieve individual, organizational, and community goals. The goal of employee placement is to contribute adequately to the development of human resource competencies within the organization. The accuracy of employee placement greatly affects their performance. Placing employees in the right position is crucial for boosting morale and motivation (NitiseMITO 2000: 116). Motivation is a key factor in improving employee performance, as it encourages them to work to the best of their abilities in carrying out their duties. Work motivation can provide energy that mobilizes existing potential, creates high and noble desires, and promotes unity. When carrying out tasks or work in an organization, it is important to follow established rules and measures with mutual respect, understanding, and consideration for the rights and obligations of each person involved in the overall operational work process.

Improper employee placement can have several negative consequences, including decreased morale, reduced work performance, and lower productivity. Siagian (2004: 13) notes that when employees are not placed correctly, their

* Corresponding author: Nursapitri Djarati

performance may not meet management expectations or organizational demands, leading to boredom and decreased productivity. Every employee requires motivation to improve their performance.

Motivation plays a crucial role in encouraging employees to carry out their duties to the best of their abilities. High work motivation can mobilize all existing potential, create high and noble desires, and foster a sense of togetherness. Performing tasks or work within an organization must adhere to established rules and measures while maintaining mutual respect, understanding, and consideration for each other's rights and obligations throughout the operational process.

In reference to previous research conducted by Hetty Virgiany Suwinto (2016), this study examines the impact of placement and motivation on the performance of PDAM employees in the Tumban district. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 55 employees of PDAM Tumban District. The Solvin formula was used to analyze the data, and the sample for this study was determined using the proportional area random sampling technique. This technique involves randomly selecting samples from each subpopulation based on the population of employees in each subpopulation. The study employed validity, reliability, and classical assumption tests, as well as multiple linear regression and Adjusted R Square for data analysis. The results indicate that placement does not significantly affect employee performance (hypothesis 1 is not accepted), while motivation does have a significant effect on employee performance (hypothesis 2 is accepted). Additionally, placement and motivation both have a significant effect on employee performance (hypothesis 3 is accepted).

The research was carried out at the Gorontalo Province Social Service office. The Social Service is a regional apparatus organization (OPD) with a strategic role in addressing social welfare problems (PMKS) and empowering potential sources of social welfare (PSKS) as well as community empowerment.

Community Empowerment activities are services that aim to reduce social problems and improve the fulfillment of basic needs for PMKS/poor people. However, the placement of employees at the Social and Women's Empowerment Service is still ineffective due to several problems, such as employees being placed in positions that do not match their backgrounds and filling structural positions that do not align with their specified education. Additionally, employee motivation is a crucial factor that can impact organizational performance. The suitability of placement and work motivation are determining factors for success in a company. Ignoring these factors can have detrimental consequences for achieving company goals, resulting in low ability and willingness to complete tasks, as well as low employee morale.

1.1. Problem identification

- Employee placement often does not align with their educational background.
- The motivation provided by leaders has not resulted in improved employee performance.
- Employee Task Completion Has Not Been Optimal.

1.2. Hypothesis

The study hypotheses are as follows: 1) Job placement variables have an influence on employee performance variables at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office; 2) Work motivation variables influence performance variables at the same office; 3) There is a joint effect of job placement variables and work motivation variables on employee performance variables at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office.

2. Methods

This study employs quantitative research methods and a descriptive research design to provide an overview of the impact of placement and work motivation on employee performance. The data analysis technique used is multiple regression.

The research was conducted at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office for three months, from August to October 2023. The activities carried out during this period are: 1) Proposal preparation, 2) Proposal revision, 3) Instrument preparation, 4) Collection of research data, 5) Analysis of research data, 6) Preparation of draft research reports, 7) Consolidation of guidance, and 8) Examination.

3. Hasil dan pembahasan

3.1. The Impact of Job Placement on Employee Performance

According to the t -test analysis, there is a positive and significant influence, as indicated by the coefficient value of the placement variable (2.858) being greater than the t -table value (0.677). The coefficient of determination test shows a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.554, indicating a relationship of 0.307 between the dependent variable (employee performance) and the independent variable (placement). It can be concluded that there is a moderate correlation between placement and employee performance. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.307 indicates that the independent variable (placement) affects the dependent variable (employee performance) by 30.7%, while the remaining 69.3% is influenced by other variables outside of this study.

The influence of job placement on employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office is direct. The presence or absence of placement in accordance with the employee's field of education does not affect employee performance in completing tasks. Additionally, employees gain sufficient knowledge to complete all assigned tasks properly during the training period.

According to Rivai (2009: 210), employee placement involves assigning employees to specific work positions, particularly for new employees. This also applies to existing employees who may need to maintain their current position or move to a different one. Therefore, placement in this context encompasses promotion, transfer, and demotion. This is supported by Atkhan's (2013) research on The Effect of Job Placement on Employee Performance at the Plantation Service of East Kalimantan Province, which indicates that there is no positive correlation between job placement and performance.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that there is a correlation between job placement and employee performance at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office. The question remains whether or not placement has a direct impact on employee performance.

3.2. The Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance

According to the t -test analysis, there is a positive and significant influence, as indicated by the motivation variable coefficient value (6.848) being greater than the t -table value (0.677). This suggests that motivation can improve employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office.

It is important to note that motivation and performance have a close relationship, as motivation is an individual's drive to behave and carry out work activities. Motivation is necessary to carry out work effectively and achieve expected results. According to the correlation coefficient test (R) of 0.715, there is a strong relationship (0.511) between employee performance and motivation.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.511, indicating that the independent variable (motivation) affects the dependent variable (employee performance) by 51.1%, while the remaining 48.9% is influenced by other variables outside the scope of this study.

Rivai (2004) supports the results of this study, arguing that motivation can effectively drive employees to work hard and achieve their goals, ultimately improving employee performance and contributing to the achievement of company goals. Employee motivation is crucial for ensuring that employees approach their work with enthusiasm and pleasure, and can foster healthy competition among colleagues striving to become outstanding employees. To ensure high levels of employee performance, it is important to maintain a motivated workforce.

This is evident in the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office, where work motivation variables have been found to influence performance variables. The presence or absence of motivation can significantly impact employee performance.

3.3. The Impact of Job Employee and Motivation on Employee Performance

According to Hasibuan (2009: 63), there is a mutual relationship between placement and motivation to perform. Proper placement can provide motivation, generate enthusiasm, and increase work morale for employees, resulting in optimal work performance and the development of employee creativity. It is important to ensure that job placement is appropriate to achieve work passion and mental focus.

The study results suggest that employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office is positively affected by placement and motivation. The contribution of placement and motivation to employee performance is significant ($\Delta R^2 = 0.553$), accounting for 53.3% of the variance. The hypothesis is accepted, indicating that placement and motivation have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The absence of a maximum contribution indicates that there are still numerous other variables that impact employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office, aside from placement and motivation.

High work motivation leads to greater enthusiasm and effort. According to Hasibuan (2003: 55), work motivation and work discipline are crucial for employees to work hard and achieve high productivity.

Employee performance is strongly linked to motivation. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.553 indicates that the independent variable (motivation) accounts for 55.3% of the variance in the dependent variable (employee performance), while the remaining 44.7% is influenced by other variables not included in this study. Additionally, the results show that placement and motivation have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The absence of a maximum contribution indicates that there are still numerous other variables that impact the performance of employees at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office, aside from placement and motivation.

From the aforementioned discussion, it can be concluded that placement and motivation, when combined, have a positive and significant impact on employee performance. However, the performance of employees at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office is influenced by various factors beyond placement and motivation. These factors include turnover, organizational commitment, compensation, organizational culture, work environment, and other variables.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research data and discussion, several research conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- The study found that Placement (X_1) has a positive and significant impact on employee performance (Y) at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office. The coefficient of determination value is 0.554, indicating a relationship of 0.307 or 30.7% between the dependent variable (employee performance) and the independent variable (placement). The remaining 69.3% are influenced by other variables outside the scope of this research. There is a correlation between work placement and employee performance at the Gorontalo Provincial Social Service Office.
- The study found that work motivation (X_2) has a positive and significant impact on employee performance (Y) at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office. The coefficient of determination value of 0.715 indicates a relationship of 0.511 or 51.1% between the dependent variable (employee performance) and the independent variable (motivation), while the remaining 48.9% is influenced by other variables outside the scope of this research. It can be concluded that there is a close relationship between motivation and employee performance at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office.
- Simultaneously or together, Placement (X_1) and Motivation (X_2) have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y) at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office. The contribution of Placement and Motivation to explaining employee performance is (ΔR^2) 0.553, which means that they contribute 53.3% to employee performance, while the remaining 44.7% is influenced by other variables outside this research. The hypothesis that placement and motivation have a positive and significant effect on employee performance can be accepted simultaneously. However, it is important to note that other variables may also influence the performance of employees at the Gorontalo Province Social Service Office, such as turnover, organizational commitment, compensation, organizational culture, work environment, and other factors outside the scope of this research.

4.1. Suggestion

Based on the presented conclusions, the following suggestions are recommended for this research:

- The Gorontalo Provincial Social Service office should prioritize the well-being of its employees, particularly in terms of employee placement, to ensure efficient and effective delivery of community services.
- The Gorontalo Province Social Service should motivate employees by providing opportunities for further education and offering awards or rewards to enhance their performance in daily duties.
- Future researchers should examine other variables that may influence employee performance, such as turnover, organizational commitment, compensation, organizational culture, work environment, or other variables.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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